

Cross-Scale Echoes of Ultra-Fast Oscillations in the Human Brain

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Abstract

Ultra-fast oscillations (UFOs) are brief bursts of high-frequency (2–8 kHz) activity recorded using depth electrodes in epileptic brain tissue. While reliably detected at small scales using microelectrodes, UFOs have thus far not been observed at larger scales using macroelectrodes. Here we propose that, if we take the effects of cross-scale attenuation into account, faint echoes of these bursting patterns can be detected in macroelectrode signals. To model this cross-scale effect, we extend the classical damped wave equation to include an explicit scale coordinate governed by the dilation operator and use Green's functions to obtain an expression for the spectral echo expected at the macroelectrode scale. This echo takes the form of a carrier envelope modulated by the temporal structure of the original micro-scale bursting event. We test these predictions in human intracranial recordings from eleven epilepsy patients implanted with both micro and macroelectrodes. We find that statistically significant echoes are rare, being confirmed in two out of eleven patients and appearing in 2% of all tested micro-macro pairs.

Introduction

Ultra-fast oscillations (UFOs) are brief bursts of activity in the 2–8 kHz range that originate in epileptic mesiotemporal structures¹ and occur at substantially higher frequencies than other reported bursting patterns such as ripples (80–250 Hz) and fast ripples (250–500 Hz)^{2–4}. UFOs are reliably detected using microelectrodes but are absent in macroelectrode recordings, leading to their common interpretation as a fundamentally micro-scale phenomenon. However, we propose that the original microscopic burst does not vanish at larger scales, but rather transforms into slower, spatially broader echoes as it propagates outward from smaller to larger structures in the brain. Here we derive the power spectrum that a UFO echo is expected to produce at the macroscale and use this as a template to search for echoes in empirical macroelectrode recordings.

It is well established that micro-scale neural events can have macro-scale correlates. For instance, microseizures — discharges confined to single microelectrodes — can precede clinical seizures visible on macroelectrodes⁵. More broadly, high-frequency bursts generated by local neuronal assemblies have been proposed as electrophysiological substrates of engram activity⁶. Recent work has shown that such bursts co-occur across widespread cortical

areas during memory processing, suggesting that micro-scale activity routinely organizes into large-scale patterns⁷. What has been lacking, however, is a model describing precisely how a signal is expected to change as it propagates across scales. Our framework addresses this gap by deriving the predicted transformation from first principles.

In building the theoretical framework underlying cross-scale echoes, we begin with the damped wave equation commonly used to describe neural field propagation^{8,9} along a spatial coordinate and adapt it to describe instead how activity propagates across scale. To this end, we note that, unlike spatial position, the coordinates associated with scale do not shift — they stretch. Formally, position transforms additively under translation, whereas scale transforms multiplicatively under dilation. The natural coordinate for scale is therefore logarithmic rather than linear (Box 1).

Box 1: *Summary transformation properties of space and scale.*

	Space	Scale
Transformation	Additive	Multiplicative
Generator	Translation	Dilation
Geometry	Euclidean	Logarithmic

In contrast to models that describe neural dynamics at a fixed spatial scale^{10,11}, we model cross-scale propagation by replacing the spatial translation generator in the wave equation with the dilation operator, and use a Green's function approach to derive the spectral signature of the UFO echo expected in macroelectrode recordings.

Methods

Theoretical Framework: We describe a neural variable $z(t, x)$ evolving in time and propagating along a spatial coordinate x using the standard damped wave equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} + 2\gamma \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} + \omega^2 z - v_x^2 T^2 z = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ω is the natural angular frequency, γ is the damping rate, v_x is the propagation speed, and $T = \partial/\partial x$ the generator of infinitesimal translations in space.

In contrast with the additive transformations of the spatial coordinate x , a scale coordinate s transforms multiplicatively, with a generator of infinitesimal dilations given by:

$$D = s \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \quad (2)$$

Our key modelling assumption is that cross-scale propagation obeys the same structure as spatial propagation, if we replace the spatial translation generator T in Eq. (1) with the dilation generator D in Eq. (2):

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} + 2\gamma \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} + \omega^2 z - v_s^2 D^2 z = 0 \quad (3)$$

where v_s is the cross-scale propagation speed.

Applying the dilation operator in Eq. (2) twice, we obtain:

$$D^2 = s^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial s^2} + s \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \quad (4)$$

Substituting Eq. (4) into Eq. (3) gives the explicit cross-scale wave equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} + 2\gamma \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} + \omega^2 z - v_s^2 \left(s^2 \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial s^2} + s \frac{\partial z}{\partial s} \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

This describes how activity changes as it propagates across scales.

Switching to log-scale coordinates $u = \log s$ simplifies the dilation operator into an additive transformation $s \frac{\partial}{\partial s} = \frac{\partial}{\partial u}$ and $D^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial u^2}$, such that Eq. (5) reduces to:

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} + 2\gamma \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} + \omega^2 z - v_s^2 \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial u^2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Therefore, upon adopting logarithmic coordinates, the cross-scale wave equation in Eq. (6) becomes equivalent in form to the spatial wave equation in Eq. (1).

Next, we model the UFO by taking this homogeneous expression and considering its response to a rapid sequence of $N + 1$ impulses separated by the inverse burst frequency $1/\Omega$. Given that this burst has a total duration τ , originates at a microscale s_μ (corresponding to $u_\mu = \log s_\mu$) and occurs at times $t_n = n/\Omega$, we can consider Eq. (6) as being driven by an input $\delta(s - s_\mu) \sum_{n=0}^N \delta(t - t_n)$, where $N = \lceil \tau\Omega \rceil$, the driven form of Eq. (6) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial t^2} + 2\gamma \frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \omega^2 G - v_s^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial u^2} = s_\mu^{-1} \delta(u - u_\mu) \sum_{n=0}^N \delta(t - t_n) \quad (7)$$

where the factor s_μ^{-1} on the right-hand side arises from expressing the spatial delta function $\delta(s - s_\mu)$ in logarithmic coordinates.

We note that Eq. (7) takes the form of the 1-D driven Klein–Gordon equation, with a known causal Green's function¹² given by:

$$G = \frac{1}{2v_s} e^{-\gamma t} J_0 \left(\sqrt{(\omega^2 - \gamma^2) (t^2 - v_s^{-2} |u - u_\mu|^2)} \right) H(t - v_s^{-1} |u - u_\mu|) \quad (8)$$

where J_0 is the zeroth-order Bessel function and H is the causal Heaviside step. This describes a decaying wavefront spreading in the (t, u) plane.

We then consider a macroscopic observation scale u_M , at which point the total UFO echo is simply given by the sum of the Green's responses in Eq. (8) to each delta impulse:

$$z_{echo} = \sum_{n=0}^N G(t - t_n, u_M; u_\mu) \quad (9)$$

We now move to the frequency domain, given that the theory predicts that a UFO should reappear at the macroscale with a specific spectral signature shaped by the Green's function. Applying a Fourier transform in time to Eq. (7) we obtain:

$$\alpha(\sigma)\tilde{G} - v_s^2 \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{G}}{\partial u^2} = s_\mu^{-1} \delta(u - u_\mu) \quad (10)$$

where σ is the Fourier frequency and $\alpha(\sigma) = \omega^2 - \sigma^2 - 2i\gamma\sigma$. Eq. (10) yields the frequency-domain form of a 1-D Klein-Gordon operator in log-scale space.

Away from the point source at $u = u_\mu$, the right-hand side of Eq. (10) is zero and the resultant expression has exponential solutions of the form $e^{-q(\sigma)|u-u_\mu|}$ with a complex scale-propagation wavenumber $q(\sigma) = v_s^{-1} \sqrt{\alpha(\sigma)}$. The causal branch is selected by imposing $Im\{q\} > 0$, ensuring that energy decays with increasing scale distance. Imposing the standard jump condition across the delta source at $u = u_\mu$ determines the normalization, yielding the frequency-domain Green's function:

$$\tilde{G} = \frac{1}{2v_s^2 q(\sigma)} e^{-q(\sigma)|u_M - u_\mu|} \quad (11)$$

Taking the Fourier transform of the macroscale time domain UFO signal in Eq. (9) gives $\tilde{G}(\sigma) \sum_{n=0}^N e^{-i\sigma n/\Omega}$. This summation has a closed form expression given by $e^{-i\sigma N/2\Omega} \sin[(N+1)\sigma/(2\Omega)] / \sin[\sigma/(2\Omega)]$, with an absolute value yielding the Dirichlet kernel:

$$D_N(\sigma) = \left| \frac{\sin[(N+1)\sigma/(2\Omega)]}{\sin[\sigma/(2\Omega)]} \right| \quad (12)$$

This represents the spectral envelope created purely by the periodic timing of the impulses.

Combining Eqs. (11) and (12), we obtain the macroscopic power spectrum $P(\sigma) = |\tilde{G}(\sigma)|^2 D_N(\sigma)^2$:

$$P(\sigma) = \frac{e^{-2Re\{q(\sigma)\}|u_M - u_\mu|}}{4v_s^4 |q(\sigma)|^2} \left| \frac{\sin[(N+1)\sigma/(2\Omega)]}{\sin[\sigma/(2\Omega)]} \right|^2 \quad (13)$$

The first factor $e^{-2Re\{q(\sigma)\}|u_M - u_\mu|}$ describes exponential attenuation with scale separation, the second $\frac{1}{4v_s^4 |q(\sigma)|^2}$ shapes the carrier envelope through the complex wavenumber, and the third $\left| \frac{\sin[(N+1)\sigma/(2\Omega)]}{\sin[\sigma/(2\Omega)]} \right|^2$ encodes the comb-like spectral structure of the original burst.

SEEG recordings: Intracranial SEEG recordings were obtained from eleven epilepsy patients across three clinical centers: Mayo Clinic (Rochester, MN; n=5), Brno Epilepsy Center (Brno, Czech Republic; n=3), and Wroclaw Medical University Hospital (Wroclaw, Poland; n=3). All patients were implanted with hybrid depth electrodes carrying both clinical macrocontacts and research microcontacts. Electrode designs and acquisition systems differed across centers and are described separately below.

Mayo Clinic (Patient IDs MAYO00038, MAYO00397, MAYO00448, MAYO00452, MAYO00453): Custom hybrid depth electrodes (AD-Tech Medical Instrument Corporation, Racine, WI) were used, based on standard four- and eight-contact clinical depth electrode

designs. Each electrode consists of a 1.3 mm diameter polyurethane shaft with platinum/iridium (Pt/Ir) macrocontacts (2.3 mm long, 5 or 10 mm center-to-centre spacing, surface area 9.4 mm²). The eight-contact design carries 8–24 microcontacts positioned radially along the shaft between 1–4 macrocontacts; the four-contact design carries 16 microcontacts. Each electrode additionally has a bundle of 9 Pt/Ir microwires (40 μm diameter, surface area 10⁻³ mm², 0.5–1 mm spacing) protruding 1–3 mm from the shaft tip.

Patients received one hybrid electrode in each temporal lobe; in one patient, subdural strips and additional intracerebral electrodes were implanted to monitor parietal and occipital cortex. Electrode positions were verified using CT with electrodes in situ. Signals were acquired on a Neuralynx system (Neuralynx Inc., Bozeman, MT) using a wideband DC-coupled analog front end (passband DC to ~9 kHz) and digitized at 32 kHz. Macrocontact signals were low-pass filtered (Bartlett–Hanning, 1 kHz) and downsampled to 5 kHz. A stainless steel subgaleal suture placed at the scalp vertex between the 10–20 Cz and Fz positions served as the common reference.

Brno Epilepsy Center (Patient IDs FNUS00061, FNUS00072, FNUS00079): In addition to standard multi-contact platinum depth electrodes (0.8 mm diameter, 2 mm macrocontact length, 1.5 mm intercontact distance; Microdeep, DIXI Medical, Besançon, France, or Depth Electrodes Range, ALCIS, Besançon, France), one custom hybrid depth electrode (2069-ECP-8C6-35T06-2G-26, ALCIS, Besançon, France) was implanted in each patient. This hybrid electrode has eight macrocontacts (surface area 5 mm²) and six microcontacts (surface area 1075 μm²) positioned radially along the shaft between the first and third macrocontacts.

Each patient received 3–14 depth electrodes, implanted orthogonally in the temporal lobes and, where clinically indicated, in the frontal lobes. Electrode positions were verified using co-registered MRI and CT with electrodes in situ. Signals were recorded using a 192-channel research acquisition system (M&I BrainScope, Prague, Czech Republic) at a sampling rate of 25 kHz with a dynamic range of ±25 mV. The system uses an oversampling analog-to-digital converter with an internal low-pass decimation filter providing anti-aliasing at the final 25 kHz output rate. The acquisition unit was battery-powered to eliminate line noise, and microcontacts were connected to high-impedance amplifiers (>1 GΩ).

Standard epilepsy monitoring unit protocols were followed, with additional measures to minimize electromagnetic interference and 50 Hz power grid contamination; no shielded environment was used. The ground electrode served as the reference for microcontacts; common average reference across all macrocontacts was used for macrocontacts.

Wroclaw Medical University Hospital (Patient IDs: WROC00001, WROC00003, WROC00004). Custom hybrid depth electrodes (AD-Tech Medical Instrument Corporation, Racine, WI) of two designs were used. Both share the same 1.3 mm diameter polyurethane shaft with Pt/Ir macrocontacts (2.3 mm long, 5 or 10 mm centre-to-centre spacing, surface area 9.4 mm²) described above for Mayo Clinic. The six-contact design carries 10 microcontacts positioned radially along the shaft between macrocontacts 1–3. The eight-contact Behnke-Fried design has a bundle of 8 Pt/Ir microwires (40 μm diameter) protruding 1–3 mm from the electrode tip. Patients were implanted with one or two six-contact hybrid electrodes in the temporal or frontal lobe, and three to four Behnke-Fried electrodes in the temporal cortex unilaterally, with additional standard clinical depth electrodes in other lobes as clinically indicated. Electrode positions were verified using CT with electrodes in situ.

Signals were acquired on a Neuralynx system (Neuralynx Inc., Bozeman, MT) using a wideband DC-coupled analog front end (passband DC to ~9 kHz) and digitized at 32 kHz.

Macrocontact signals were downsampled to 5 kHz. A subgaleal strip of four macrocontacts placed at the scalp vertex between the 10–20 Cz and Fz positions served as the common reference for macrocontacts. Microcontact signals were referenced locally to a quiescent microchannel showing no neuronal spiking or other neural activity.

Software. EEGWave was used for interactive graphical analysis of multichannel data, custom Python scripts for batch processing and event detection, and R for statistical analysis.

UFO detection. Detection was performed in a sliding 30-second window. A spectrogram of the input signal was computed using an FFT window of 15 ms with 97% overlap and linear detrending of each windowed segment. Each frequency row of the spectrogram was normalized by dividing by its running median in a 1-second sliding window. Analysis was restricted to the 2–8 kHz range, keeping the maximum analyzed frequency below the practical limit of $f_s/3$ and within the passband of the recording hardware. A one-dimensional detection signal was created by summing all rows of this normalized, frequency-bounded spectrogram. Peaks exceeding five times the 99th percentile of this detection signal were identified as candidate events, and the region around each peak bounded by its inflection points was marked as a putative high-frequency event. For each candidate detection, two quantities were retained for further analysis: (i) the original raw signal within the detection window, and (ii) a spectral profile created by summing all time columns of the normalised spectrogram within the detection boundaries¹³.

Classification. Each candidate event was classified as either rhythmic or non-rhythmic based on the ratio of the maximum to the mean of its spectral profile. Events with a ratio exceeding 10 were classified as rhythmic, indicating a dominant oscillatory frequency; events below this threshold were classified as non-rhythmic. This ratio served as a tuning parameter and was chosen heuristically: lowering it increased the number of detections but reduced the dominance of the peak frequency. At a threshold of 10, $34.8 \pm 22.1\%$ of primary detections were retained.

Rhythmic events were further subdivided into two morphological types. Type I events showed a smooth amplitude envelope (gradual rise and fall) oscillating within a single frequency band, appearing as a circular or ellipsoidal region in the spectrogram. Type II events showed an abrupt amplitude onset followed by a slow decay, often accompanied by a shift in the signal mean, producing a vertical stripe in the spectrogram followed by sustained activity in a narrow frequency band. To distinguish between these types, the raw signal of each detection was analysed as follows. The point at which the absolute value of the signal derivative reached half its maximum was designated the true onset.

Two flanking sections were defined: section 1 spanning one quarter of the detection length before the true onset, and section 2 spanning one quarter after it. If the true onset fell outside the central half of the detection (before 1/4 or after 3/4 of the total length), the event was automatically classified as Type I. Otherwise, an event was classified as Type II if either condition 1: $\frac{std(section\ 2)}{std(section\ 1)} > 10$ or condition 2: $\frac{std(section\ 2)}{std(section\ 1)} > 4.5$ and $\frac{|mean(section\ 1) - mean(section\ 2)|}{std(section\ 1)} > 1$ are met. The first condition captures a sudden increase in amplitude variability; the second captures a combined increase in variability and shift in signal mean. The thresholds (10 and 4.5) were chosen heuristically. Using these criteria, approximately 35% of rhythmic events were classified as Type II and 65% as Type I.

Only Type I events — clear rhythmic oscillations with a smooth amplitude envelope with peak frequency above 2 kHz — were used in the subsequent analyses.

Spectral echo detection. For each microelectrode UFO event, we extracted the corresponding macroscale time series from the nearest macroelectrode. Two windows were defined per event: a 200 ms pre-UFO baseline and a 200 ms post-UFO segment. Both windows were demeaned and linearly detrended. The theory predicts that a UFO burst will reappear at the macroscale with a spectral shape determined by the frequency-domain Green's function. Taking the squared magnitude of \tilde{G} in Eq. (11) and retaining only the frequency-dependent terms (constant prefactors cancel after template normalisation) yields the spectral envelope:

$$|\tilde{G}(\sigma)|^2 \sim \frac{1}{(\omega^2 - \sigma^2)^2 + (2\gamma\sigma)^2} \quad (14)$$

This is the power spectrum of a damped oscillator with a resonant peak at the echo frequency $\omega_{echo} = \sqrt{\omega^2 - \gamma^2}$. For each patient, this template was evaluated using fixed model parameters ($f_0 = 75 \text{ Hz}$, $\gamma = 40 \text{ s}^{-1}$), normalised to unit energy, and restricted to the analysis frequency band [60, 100] Hz.

For each window, we estimated the power spectral density using Welch's method (100 ms segments, 50% overlap, minimum 512-point FFT). The template was projected onto each empirical PSD via a non-negative scalar gain: $A = \max(0, \mathbb{T}^\top \mathbb{P})$, where \mathbb{T} is the unit-normalised template and \mathbb{P} the empirical PSD within the analysis band. The echo detection score for each event was defined as $\log_{10} \frac{A_{post}}{A_{base}}$, where a positive score indicates greater template-matching power in the post-UFO window relative to baseline.

Statistical testing. Statistical significance was assessed using a time-shifted empirical null procedure. For each micro–macro electrode pair, the echo detection scores across all K UFO events were averaged to produce a single empirical statistic. A null distribution was constructed by repeating this procedure 10,000 times at randomly sampled time points on the same macroelectrode channel: in each null iteration, K time points were drawn uniformly from the recording, excluding windows overlapping any detected UFO, and each was processed identically to the real events (baseline extraction, PSD estimation, template projection, and scoring). The K null scores were averaged to produce a single null statistic per iteration, yielding a distribution of 10,000 null means.

A one-sided p-value for each pair was computed as $p = \frac{1+n_{exceed}}{N_{eff}+1}$, where n_{exceed} is the number of null means greater than or equal to the empirical mean and N_{eff} is the number of valid null iterations, with the +1 correction ensuring a valid Monte Carlo p-value. Multiple comparisons across pairs within each patient were corrected using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure at a false discovery rate of $q = 0.05$.

Results

We tested a total of 100 micro–macro electrode pairs for evidence of cross-scale UFO echoes across eleven patients. Empirical echo scores were compared with a time-shifted empirical null distribution, with significance assessed using Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction ($q = 0.05$) applied within each patient across tested micro–macro pairs. Two patients each showed one significant micro–macro pair, corresponding to 2 of 100 tested pairs across all patients exhibiting evidence of cross-scale echoes (Table 1).

Table 1: Total number of UFOs and micro-macro electrode pairs tested for each of the eleven patients. Red asterisks indicate that a single pair survived multiple comparison correction (FDR). Patient MAYO00452 did not meet the minimum data requirement for statistical testing, as indicated by the zero usable micro-macro pairs.

Patient ID	UFOs	Pairs
WROC00001	93	10
WROC00003	119	11
WROC00004	47	5
FNUS00061	16	1
FNUS00072	19	3
FNUS00079	89	5
MAYO00038	256	32
MAYO00397	306	24
MAYO00448	75	8
MAYO00452	11	0
MAYO00453	20	1

The remaining nine patients showed no significant pairs after FDR correction, consistent with adequate control of the false positive rate by the null procedure.

In patient WROC00003, 119 UFOs were identified, yielding 11 testable micro–macro electrode pairs. One pair — microelectrode CSC73 paired with macroelectrode SMAL1 — showed a significant cross-scale echo after FDR correction ($p = 0.0001$, empirical mean score 0.22, null mean -0.001 ± 0.05). A second pair (CSC69–SMAAL1) was significant at the uncorrected level ($p = 0.01$) but did not survive FDR correction.

In patient WROC00004, 47 UFOs were identified, yielding 5 testable micro–macro electrode pairs. One pair — microelectrode CSC65 paired with macroelectrode AMG1 — showed a significant cross-scale echo after FDR correction ($p = 0.0096$, empirical mean score 0.31, null mean 0.002 ± 0.13).

To illustrate this result, Fig. 1 shows a single UFO event in patient WROC00003, for which the corresponding macrochannel exhibited a post-UFO power increase in the high-gamma range. This boost closely followed the shape predicted by the theoretical Green’s function envelope, consistent with the presence of a scale-propagated echo.

Fig. 1: Micro (top) and macro (bottom) traces from patient WROC00003, spanning 200 ms before UFO onset to 200 ms after UFO cessation. The red vertical bar marks the UFO. The right inset shows the UFO in the microelectrode recording on an expanded timescale (± 5 ms around the event). The left inset shows the baseline (grey) and post-UFO (black) power spectra alongside the theoretical Green’s function template (red dashed). The echo detection score reflects the projection of each spectrum onto this template; here the post-UFO projection exceeds the baseline, illustrating one of the events contributing to the statistically significant average effect for this micro macro pair.

We note that statistical significance is assessed at the micro-macro pair level by averaging scores across all UFOs, whereas Fig. 1 illustrates a single representative UFO event for visualization purposes.

Discussion

We introduce a geometric framework for understanding how ultra-fast oscillations (UFOs) transform as they propagate across scales in the brain. The theoretical foundation lies in replacing the spatial translation operator in the classical damped wave equation with the dilation operator. This yields a cross-scale wave equation whose Green's function describes how microscopic kilohertz bursts give rise to lower-frequency macroscopic echoes. The model predicts a characteristic spectral fingerprint at the macroscale: a carrier envelope shaped by the Green's function, modulated by a Dirichlet kernel encoding the finite burst structure of the initiating UFO.

The model we propose indicates that UFOs undergo exponential attenuation as they propagate across scale, resulting in sparse echoes in macroelectrode recordings. Statistically significant echoes were rare, being confirmed in 2 out of 100 micro–macro electrode pairs and confined to two out of eleven patients. It is possible that electrode arrays with denser, co-localized micro and macro contacts could yield higher detection rates. Furthermore, stimulation experiments that induce controlled microscale high-frequency bursts would provide a complementary test, allowing systematic investigation of the conditions under which predicted macroscopic echoes appear.

The average firing rate recorded from microchannel CSC73 (located within the macroelectrode SMAL1) and from CSC65 (within macroelectrode AMG1) did not differ from the activity observed in other microchannels. This indicates that the observed activity does not reflect simultaneous spike events across different recording channels¹⁴. Furthermore, we found that there was no positive correlation between the spiking activity of the three single units isolated from these microchannels and physiological high-frequency oscillations (HFOs) detected on the corresponding macroelectrodes. To the contrary, these neurons exhibited weaker correlations with HFO onset than neurons recorded from other microchannels. This indicates that the UFO echo effect is not explained by a correlation between neuronal spiking and HFOs.

The present framework connects to a growing body of evidence that micro-scale neural events organize into macro-scale patterns. For instance, seizures confined to single microelectrodes can evolve into clinical seizures visible at the macroscale⁵. Furthermore, microscale high-frequency oscillation (HFO) bursts have been proposed as electrophysiological substrates of macro-scale memory engrams⁶, and coincident HFO bursting across cortical regions has been shown to coordinate large-scale memory processing⁷.

Here, rather than treating the relationship between scales as purely empirical, we provide a mathematical framework that describes the expected spectral transformation accompanying this micro-to-macro propagation. Our results suggest that macroelectrode recordings may routinely contain faint, spectrally transformed echoes of microscale activity.

Code Availability

All relevant code is made available at the following repositories:

<https://github.com/allavailablepubliccode/UFO>

<https://zenodo.org/records/18193447>

Funding

The authors acknowledge support from Masaryk University, the International Clinical Research Center (ICRC), St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, project nr. LX22NPO5107

(MEYS): Financed by European Union – Next Generation EU. E.D.F. was supported by the Czech Health Research Agency (AZV, NW25-04-00226).

References

- 1 Brázdil, M. *et al.* Ultra fast oscillations in the human brain and their functional significance. *medRxiv*, 2023.2002. 2023.23285962 (2023).
- 2 Bragin, A., Engel Jr, J., Wilson, C. L., Fried, I. & Buzsáki, G. High-frequency oscillations in human brain. *Hippocampus* **9**, 137–142 (1999).
- 3 Jacobs, J. *et al.* High-frequency oscillations (HFOs) in clinical epilepsy. *Progress in neurobiology* **98**, 302–315 (2012).
- 4 Frauscher, B. *et al.* High-frequency oscillations: the state of clinical research. *Epilepsia* **58**, 1316–1329 (2017).
- 5 Stead, M. *et al.* Microseizures and the spatiotemporal scales of human partial epilepsy. *Brain* **133**, 2789–2797 (2010).
- 6 Kucewicz, M. T., Cimbalnik, J., Garcia-Salinas, J. S., Brazdil, M. & Worrell, G. A. High frequency oscillations in human memory and cognition: a neurophysiological substrate of engrams? *Brain* **147**, 2966–2982 (2024).
- 7 Prathapagiri, S. *et al.* Coincident bursts of high frequency oscillations across the human cortex coordinate large-scale memory processing. *BioRxiv*, 2025.2003. 2024.644989 (2025).
- 8 Jirsa, V. K. & Haken, H. A derivation of a macroscopic field theory of the brain from the quasi-microscopic neural dynamics. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena* **99**, 503–526 (1997).
- 9 Pinotsis, D. A. & Friston, K. J. Neural fields, spectral responses and lateral connections. *Neuroimage* **55**, 39–48 (2011).
- 10 Ermentrout, G. B. & Kopell, N. Parabolic bursting in an excitable system coupled with a slow oscillation. *SIAM journal on applied mathematics* **46**, 233–253 (1986).
- 11 Breakspear, M. Dynamic models of large-scale brain activity. *Nat Neurosci* **20**, 340–352 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4497>
- 12 Morse, P. M. & Feshbach, H. *Methods of Theoretical Physics*. (McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc., 1953).
- 13 Travnicsek, V. *et al.* in *2021 43rd annual international conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC)*. 265–268 (IEEE).
- 14 Dehnen, G. *et al.* Duplicate detection of spike events: a relevant problem in human single-unit recordings. *Brain Sciences* **11**, 761 (2021).